

DIFFERENTIATION AS A CONDITION FOR INDIVIDUALIZATION OF LEARNING IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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Annotation: The need to consider the individual characteristics of a child in foreign language lessons lies in the individual differences in those qualities of students on which the learning outcome depends: the level of knowledge, skills, learning skills and abilities, as well as properties and conditions that affect this particular student and are considered in individual cases.

Key words: individualization, differentiation, learning ability, educational skills, cognitive interest.

Аннотация: Необходимость учета индивидуальных особенностей ребенка на уроках иностранного языка заключается в индивидуальных различиях в тех качествах учащихся, от которых зависит результат обучения: уровень знаний, умений, навыков усвоения материала и способностей к обучению, а также свойства и условия, которые принимаются во внимание и влияют на данного конкретного учащегося.

Ключевые слова: индивидуализация, дифференциация, обучаемость, учебные умения, познавательный интерес.

Annotatsiya: Chet tili darolarida bolaning shaxsiy xususiyatlarini hisobga olish zarurati o'quvchilarning fazilatlaridagi individual farqlar bilan bog'liq: bilim, ko'nikma, o'rganish ko'nikmalari va qobiliyatlari darajasi, shuningdek, o'qitish natijalariga bog'liq bo'lgan, ushbu o'quvchiga ta'sir qiladigan va qabul qilinadigan xususiyatlar va sharoitlar alohida hollarda hisobga olinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: individuallashtirish, farqlash, o'rganish qobiliyati, ta'lim qobiliyatlari, kognitiv qiziqish.

The concept of modernization of Uzbek education develops the basic principles of educational policy in Uzbekistan, which are defined in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" dated 09/23/2020 No. 637-ZRU and guarantees equal rights to education for all, regardless of gender, race, nationality, language, religion, social origin, religion, personal and social status. The types of education are also

considered as preschool education and upbringing; general secondary and secondary specialized education; vocational education; higher education; postgraduate education; retraining and advanced training; extracurricular education.

Differentiation of learning is a special form of organization of learning, considering the typological individual psychological characteristics of students and the special organization of teacher–student communication, associated with such an organization of the educational process, which is characterized by variability in the content, methods and intensity of learning. In other words, differentiation is the grouping of students based on their individual characteristics or sets of characteristics for learning according to several different curricula and programs.

Individualization of learning is considering in the learning process the individual characteristics of students in all its forms and methods, regardless of what features and to what extent.

There is a relationship between the concepts of "individualization" and "differentiation", determined by the following relation: differentiation of student learning is an important condition for the individualization of the entire pedagogical process.

I.E. Unt believes that the characteristics of students, which should first be considered when individualizing learning, include:

1) Learning ability – the level of mental development of a student, the prerequisites for his teaching. Learning ability includes generalization of mental activity, economy of thinking, independence of thinking, flexibility of thinking, semantic memory, the nature of the connection between visual and abstract components of thinking [Menchinskaya 2001: 40].

2) Educational skills – special abilities (mathematics, physics, language) and giftedness as innate makings for the formation of abilities.

3) Training, consisting of both programmatic and non-programmatic knowledge, skills and abilities. Learning is distinguished by programmatic knowledge, knowledge in the field of a given subject, and non-programmatic knowledge (preliminary).

4) Cognitive interests (against the background of general educational motivation);

5) The state of health and properties of the nervous system (each of the temperaments manifests itself in different ways) [Unt 1990: 135].

Often, differentiation in teaching foreign languages is based not only on the individual characteristics of the student's personality, but also on individual gaps in his knowledge. The ability of students to learn English is not the same: one language is given easily, others — with great difficulty. It should be noted that educational material at different levels of learning can be assimilated by students of the same

class in different ways: for example, some children learn lexical material more easily due to well-developed mechanical memory, while others have better auditory perception, so they successfully cope with listening exercises.

Studying the interests and abilities of students, as well as analyzing the prospects for the development of their capabilities, is the starting point in an individual approach to teaching a foreign language.

In the practice of pedagogical activity, as a rule, the individual characteristics of a certain group of students are considered, and not an individual in which students have similar characteristics. The teacher considers only those criteria that are important from the point of view of learning effectiveness. These include, for example, mental abilities, features of the development of the central nervous system. Thus, an individual approach is implemented not in the course of all educational activities, but only sporadically.

Individualization of learning is not only episodic, but also systemic. Episodic individual work is carried out when children are not focused on this type of activity. It can arise spontaneously in response to a successful methodical technique, a problem raised by a teacher or one of the students. And in turn, systematic individual work is planned in advance, considering the intellectual characteristics of students, their attitude to learning. The teacher prepares didactic materials, determines the forms and methods of working with the class as a whole and with specific students individually in the classroom.

As for differentiated learning, in this case, each student works at the level of their abilities, overcomes quite tangible, but surmountable difficulties in mastering the material. Observations of differentiated education in schools have shown that with this approach, teachers divide students, as a rule, into "strong" and "weak" [Rabunsky 2000: 154].

Internal differentiation is carried out within the school (by age, accelerated learning class and alignment class). In lesson 10, it manifests itself in the fact that the teacher chooses some feature or combination of them and on this basis the children are divided into groups:

- training groups (high – "5.4"; medium – "3.4"; low – "2.3");
- with the appropriate task;
- according to the rate of assimilation ("strong-weak" are grouped to stimulate students).

External differentiation is carried out according to interests and inclinations (special state institutions are created where inclinations and interests are considered).

In working with students, such forms of differentiated learning can be used as: - the use of tasks of varying degrees of complexity;
- using variants of the same type of tasks;

- reading texts of varying difficulty;
- providing various assistance to students when completing the same task;
- different times to complete the same task;
- various types of supports;
- performing exercises on individual cards.

These techniques develop the abilities of students, form the skills of their creative speech-thinking activity in the classroom, which helps to identify and develop the reserves of the child's personality.

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